

Electrolyte Effects and Stability of Zn/Li Dual-Ion Batteries with Water-in-Salt Electrolytes

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Abstract

Aqueous zinc-ion batteries have emerged as promising candidates for safe and cost-effective energy storage, yet their performance remains constrained by electrode stability and electrolyte composition. In this study, we investigate the electrochemical behavior of various electrode materials utilizing water-in-salt dual-ion electrolytes. Our findings highlight the critical influence of substrate materials on electrochemical stability, with titanium exhibiting superior anodic stability compared to, e.g., aluminum. Furthermore, we demonstrate the feasibility of LiFePO₄ as a positive electrode, revealing a redox potential of 1.17 V vs. Zn²⁺/Zn in chloride-based electrolyte, which shifts positively with increasing lithium concentration. The observed potential variation with electrolyte composition underscores the need for optimized formulations to enhance the battery performance. Additionally, while LiMnPO₄ offers a higher theoretical voltage, its cycling stability remains limited, suggesting that material modifications are necessary. Finally, we highlight the overlooked impact of electrolyte impurities on battery performance, emphasizing the importance of high-purity electrolyte components. These insights contribute to the development of more stable and efficient Zn-ion batteries, paving the way for their practical deployment in energy storage applications.

Keywords: Zinc-ion battery; Phosphate olivines; Water in salt electrolyte, Zinc chloride, Impurities

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1. Introduction

Aqueous rechargeable Zn-ion batteries offer a promising alternative to conventional Li-ion systems, particularly for grid-scale applications, due to their safety, affordability, and environmental friendliness. Yet, these benefits are remunerated by smaller voltages and capacities of the current devices. The Zn-ion battery was discovered by Shoi et al. in 1988 [1], but there was a moderate progress until 2012, when another paper by Xu et al. [2] triggered an exponential growth of scientific publications till the present. Zinc has the standard electrochemical potential of -0.762 V (compared to -3.04 V for Li) and a theoretical capacity of 820 mAh/g (5855 mAh/dm³) from the reaction:

In practical batteries, the reaction (1) is often complicated by dendrite formation, “dead zinc” issue, corrosion and hydrogen evolution [3-6]. The overall capacity of the Zn-ion battery is perceptibly limited by the positive electrode, whose active material has a typical theoretical capacity of around 150-170 mAh/g. Hence, numerous systems were investigated during the last decade [7, 8]. Of special interest is the Zn/CO₂ battery, which was reported recently by Liu et al. [8]. A “true” Zn-ion battery employs reversible intercalation of Zn²⁺ into suitable host structures, such as α-MnO₂ [2]:

(The system is virtually identical to the classical Leclanché or alkaline batteries, but the latter use different forms of MnO₂, and the battery chemistry is based on irreversible conversion reactions). Another example of a Zn-intercalation material is the layered ZnMn₃O₇ which can accommodate up to 1.23 Zn-ions per formula unit (≈ 170 mAh/g) [9]. In general, the distinction of simple topotactic intercalation/insertion from more complex conversion processes can be an issue in various real systems [10, 11]. Recently, Zhu et al. [12] proposed a novel Zn-battery concept in which a special positive electrode, such as the pre-zincified MnO₂, drives the zinc plating (Eq. 1) on an initially zinc-free substrate. This so-called “anode-free Zn-metal battery” has since attracted noteworthy attention [4].

The reactions at the positive electrode can also be based on a ‘dual-ion’ concept [13]. In this case, the Zn plating/dissolution (Eq. 1) is interlinked to the intercalation of electrolyte counter-anions (such as ClO₄⁻) into graphite, which acts as a positive electrode in this particular case [14]. Still another model system is based on the Zn/Li dual-ion chemistry, employing the known materials from Li-ion batteries such as LiFePO₄ (olivine) (LFP) [15-18] or LiMn₂O₄ (spinel) (LMO) [15].

A manganese-substituted iron olivine, i.e., LiMn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}PO₄ was introduced into the Zn/Li dual-ion cells by Zhao et al. [17]. It allowed enhancement of the voltage of the battery, thanks to the fact that the redox potential of the Mn³⁺/Mn²⁺ couple is by ca. 0.5 V more positive compared to the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ couple in pure LFP. They used a carbon-coated material purchased from Dow Chemical Co. [17]. We assume that the original source of the C-coated LiMn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}PO₄ was the work [19] and the corresponding patent [20] co-authored by some of us. The mentioned ratio, Mn/Fe = 4, was optimized for applications in Li-ion battery [19], but no similar screening has been performed yet on the Zn-ion battery, to the best of our knowledge. Other materials for the positive electrode are various vanadium oxides, Prussian blue analogs, etc., but the charge/discharge mechanism is complicated in these cases, and often unknown [5, 21, 22].

While the early Zn-ion batteries used electrolytes having the “usual” concentrations (about 1-2 mol/dm³) the advent of strongly concentrated electrolyte solutions, the so-called “water-in-salt electrolytes” (WiSE), extended the electrochemical stability window [14, 23, 24], and improved the Coulombic efficiency and cycle stability, particularly of the negative (Zn) electrode (Eq. 1) [15]. This is due to the unique solvation-sheath structure in WiSE, which reduces water activity in these solutions. As a result, the advantageous electrolyte properties arise not only from the high electrolyte concentration but also from the type of counter-anion present. The latter is described as chaotropic (structure disrupting) or kosmotropic (structure making) [14, 23, 24]. More specifically, the suitable Zn salts for WiSE are: ZnSO₄,

$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, ZnCl_2 , $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$. (These salts are ordered - according to the Hofmeister series - from kosmotropic to chaotropic ones) [24]. An extreme case is the “molten hydrate electrolyte”, such as $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot 2.33 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (melting point 10.1°C) introduced by Chen et al. [25]. Interestingly, ZnCl_2 could also effectively prohibit the parasitic reactions on Zn-electrode [24]. These works highlight the ZnCl_2 -based electrolyte solution [3, 23, 25], which asks for a deeper study of this particular system.

The so far reported WiSE for Zn/LiFePO₄ battery included: 15 m ZnCl_2 + 1 m LiCl (the symbol ‘m’ stands for ‘molality’) [16], 30 m CH_3COOK + 3 m CH_3COOLi + 3 m $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ [15] and 21 m LiTFSI + 0.5 m ZnSO_4 , where TFSI is bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [17]. The formulation of WiSE obviously requires high-purity salts, because even trace impurities are boosted by the extreme salt concentrations used. While it is intuitive that these impurities could influence battery chemistry, they have been largely overlooked in the literature, to the best of our knowledge. This gap presents one of the motivations for the current study.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and electrodes

Anhydrous ZnCl_2 was from three different suppliers: Sigma Aldrich (puriss, p.a.); ABCR, GmbH (AB117501, anhydrous, 98%) and Lachner, s.r.o. (p.a. 98%). The FePO_4 olivine (LFP) was from SüdChemie, GmbH, Carl Roth, GmbH (p.a., battery grade) or LFP from Xiamen TOB new energy technology Co., LTD. Three batches of the latter material were used as follows: TOB-LFP-S-21 (particles size distribution D10: $< 1.5 \mu\text{m}$, D50: $4 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$, D90: $< 10 \mu\text{m}$). TOB-LFP-01 (D10: $\geq 0.35 \mu\text{m}$, D50: $0.6\text{--}1.8 \mu\text{m}$, D90: $\leq 4.5 \mu\text{m}$) and TOB-LFP-S13 (D10: $\geq 0.25 \mu\text{m}$, D50: $1.3 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, D90: $< 10 \mu\text{m}$). The MnPO_4 olivine, both pure (LMP) and carbon-coated (C-LMP; 20% carbon) was prepared by the polyol route [26, 27], and obtained from HPL, SA (now Dow Chemical Co.). The LMP material had a BET surface area of $35 \text{m}^2/\text{g}$. Figure S1A (ESI) confirms its phase purity by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The diffractogram of C-LMP is presented in Figure S1B (ESI). It is well comparable to a diffractogram reported for C-LMP [26], as well as to that of the pure LMP (Figs S1A, B). Carbon black, C65 or SuperP ($>99\%$, metal basis) were from Timcal Graphite & Carbon, Switzerland. KynarFlex 2801 fluoropolymer powder was from Arkema. $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 99\%$, p.a.) was from Carl Roth, GmbH. Other used chemicals were from Sigma Aldrich, and used as received. Zinc (0.25 mm sheet, 99.99%), aluminum, and stainless steel 316L foils were from Goodfellow, Ltd., and used as received. Glass-like carbon (GC) plates were from Alfa Aesar. Titanium foil, Grade 2 (0.1 mm thickness) was from G24i, Ltd. In some cases. Ti-grid (Goodfellow, Ltd.) was used as an electrode substrate, too. Titanium was cleaned by boiling 20 % HCl, washed with a copious amount of water and dried. The conductive glass, F-doped SnO_2 (FTO; TEC-8, Dyesol), and indium-tin oxide (ITO; Aldrich, $6\text{--}12 \Omega/\text{sq}$) were cleaned ultrasonically in ethanol, acetone, and isopropyl alcohol. (Care should be taken when assembling the electrodes from ITO, because some plates from Aldrich exhibited significant parasitic conductivity on the back side [28].)

Electrodes were prepared from a mixture of 15 wt% carbon black (C65 or SuperP), 80 wt% of the active material (LFP, LMP, or C-LMP), and 5wt% of KynarFlex, the latter was added in the form of 10% solution in N-methyl pyrrolidone. The mixture was subsequently diluted by this solvent to a consistency of viscous paste, homogenized by sonication and stirred overnight.

The slurry was then coated by doctor blading on the respective conductive substrate, using the Kapton adhesive tape for the protection of edges. The electrodes were finally dried at 120°C in vacuum. The areal mass loading was typically 0.3-5 mg/cm². Unless stated otherwise, the voltammograms are normalized in the current scale to the mass of the active electrode material.

2.2. Methods

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis employed the wavelength dispersive spectrometer Axios (Malvern-Panalytical). The spectrometer was equipped with a Rh anode end-window X-ray tube fitted with 75 μm Be window. The software SuperQ was used to collect 11 scans in vacuum using different combinations of generator settings, collimators, and crystal detectors. Peak intensities of elements were extracted by the Omnia software, and the standardless XRF analysis was performed. The analyzed powders were pressed into pellets about 5 mm thick and a diameter of 40 mm without any binding agent and covered with 4 μm polypropylene film. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was measured by Rigaku SmartLab 9kW Powder X-ray diffractometer equipped with Bragg-Brentano para-focusing optics and CuKα radiation. Electrochemical experiments were carried out using BioLogic SP300 or Autolab 302N (Metrohm) potentiostats. The reference and counter-electrodes were from Zn-foil. The electrolyte solution was aqueous 15 m ZnCl₂ or 15 m ZnCl₂ + 1 m LiCl. Comparative experiments of Li-insertion into C-LMP were carried out as in [10] employing 0.1 M LiPF₆ in ethylene carbonate (EC) + dimethylcarbonate (DMC) (1:1 by volume). The counter and reference electrodes were from Li-metal in this particular case. All electrochemical measurements were made in a closed electrochemical cell under Ar atmosphere.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Pure substrates

As mentioned in the Introduction, one of the benefits of WiSE is the extended electrochemical window, thanks to a high concentration of the solutions and chaotropic nature of the counter-anions. However, the window width depends on the electrode material, too. Figure 1 presents the voltammetric tests of several typical working electrode materials, i.e., platinum, glass-like carbon (GC), ITO, FTO, and titanium. Figure S2 (in ESI) shows comparative data for other materials, i.e., Al, Cu, and stainless steel 316L. Platinum has, expectedly, the narrowest electrochemical window, due to its electrocatalytic activity. Interestingly, the zinc dissolution/plating on Pt is also very fast; the currents are ca. five times larger, compared to those on the other materials. The anodic breakdown potential of WiSE (15 m ZnCl₂) is increasing in the series Pt < GC < ITO < FTO < Ti (Fig. 1). The high stability of Ti is still boosted in repeated voltage sweeps, presumably due to the formation of a protective semiconducting TiO₂ overlayer by anodic oxidation of Ti-metal.

On the other hand, aluminum (which is a popular substrate for positive electrodes of Li-ion batteries) exhibits the worst performance in WiSE (Fig. S2). The initial Zn plating/dissolution is quite fast at Al (the voltammetric currents are nearly doubled against those on carbon, or Ti). However, the anodic breakdown of WiSE starts already at ca. 1 V vs. Zn²⁺/Zn, and it proceeds tempestuously with massive evolution of gas bubbles (presumably Cl₂). The currents are above 200 mA/cm² (Fig. S2 in ESI), and large Zn-dendrites are formed at the edge of the Al-plate (Fig. S3 in ESI). The dendrite formation is a notorious problem of Zn-electrode [3-5, 24, 29]. It is substrate specific, with graphene exhibiting exceptional ability of epitaxial deposition of hexagonal Zn-crystals having low lattice mismatch with graphene [29]. This not only avoids dendrite growth, but also improves Coulombic efficiency and stability of Zn anodes. The

electrochemical reactions on stainless steel are analogously dramatic, though the breakdown currents are smaller than those on Al (Fig. S2).

Copper is an unsuitable substrate, either, due to its inherent electrochemical activity between ca. 0.3 and 1.2 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn (Fig. S2) which is caused by the dissolution/plating of copper. (Note that the difference in standard redox potentials of Cu and Zn is 1.102 V, which roughly matches the data in Fig. S2). The anodic breakdown of WiSE (15 m ZnCl_2) is quite significant at the stainless steel 316L, too (Fig. S2). This behavior seems to be specific for chloride-based WiSE only, because the acetate-based WiSE were reported to be stable on stainless steel at potentials up to 2.2 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn [15]. Consequently, the use of carbon paper [18] or graphite foil [17] was proposed to be preferable for the chloride-based WiSE. Ti-metal (cf. Fig. 1) is yet another promising candidate for substrates, but, surprisingly, Ti was not used very frequently for the Zn-ion batteries; an exception is the recent work by Sun et al. [9]. These authors, however, used neither chlorides nor WiSE [9].

Glass-like carbon exhibits a mediocre stability in chloride-WiSE below ca. 2.2 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . Above this potential, the anodic breakdown causes the formation of new species, presumably surface oxides on carbon, which are reducible below ca. 1.5 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn (Figs 1 and S1). In this context, we should note that carbons are ubiquitously employed as conductive additives for the fabrication of positive electrodes, see also below. Our model experiment shows that carbon is not that inert material in ZnCl_2 -WiSE, and its use in high-voltage Zn-ion batteries should be regarded with care.

3.2. LFP and LMP electrodes

Figure 2A shows cyclic voltammograms of LFP in 15 m ZnCl_2 (ABCR) + 1 m LiCl. (We indicate the source of the ZnCl_2 in parentheses since this will play an important role later.) The voltammograms exhibit just one single redox couple with a formal potential of 1.17 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . Analogous voltammograms with a formal potential of about 1.2 V were reported by Yesibolati et al. [18] in a similar medium (4 m ZnCl_2 + 3 m LiCl). On the other hand, the voltammogram of LFP in acetate-based WiSE was upshifted in the potential scale towards a formal potential of about 1.4 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . The ≈ 0.2 V upshift in the chloride-free medium was, however, not commented [15], and remains unclear at the moment. The initial capacity of LFP at slow charging/discharging was about 150 mAh/g in both cases (in acetate or chloride media) [15, 18] but dropped significantly at progressive cycling.

The good performance of LiFePO_4 in the Zn-dual-ion (WiSE) system is not reproduced for LiMnPO_4 . Figure 2B shows tiny voltammetric features near ca. 1.8 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . It is tempting to assign them to the $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ redox couple in LMP, which is expected at potentials ca. 0.5 V more positive compared to LFP [17]. (Note, however, a possible typo in ref. [17] confusing the Zn- and SCE reference electrodes). The redox couple $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ in LMO [15] is at ca. 2 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn [15], again not that far from the features observed in Fig. 2B.

A blank experiment with a pure carbon black (C65) in the same WiSE with ZnCl_2 (ABCR) exhibited nearly identical voltammetric features, too (Fig. 2C). They are reproduced for another type of carbon black (SuperP) and are independent of the addition of LiCl to the ZnCl_2 solution. These extra voltammetric features virtually disappear if the electrolyte solution is diluted ten times (Fig. 2D). It is a strong indication, that they are borne by impurities in the used ZnCl_2 . Further details about the electrochemical behavior of SuperP in diluted ZnCl_2 solution are summarized in Fig. S4 (ESI). The cyclic voltammogram is purely capacitive, translating into a

specific capacity of about 7 F/g. (This value is quite small compared to the usual value ≈ 100 F/g reported for carbon-based supercapacitors). Replacement of the Ti substrate by FTO brings no significant changes: the ‘impurity-related’ features are still visible both on the blank carbon black (Fig. S5, ESI) and on the LMP electrodes (Fig. S6, ESI), too.

Figure 3A shows the results of long-term voltammetric cycling of our optimal system, i.e. LFP (Roth) + C65 + Ti-substrate in a WiSE electrolyte using ZnCl_2 (Aldrich). After 200 voltammetric cycles, the formal potential upshifts slightly from 1.16 to 1.19 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn , and the integral charge capacity drops from 138 to 129 mAh/g. The reversibility of anodic/cathodic charge is nearly perfect, i.e., 100 %. These results are comparable to those reported from galvanostatic cycling by others [15, 17, 18]. We may estimate that the voltammetric cycle duration (1000 s, Fig. 3) is roughly mimicking the galvanostatic C-rate of 3.6 C. Notably, our system exhibits better stability at prolonged voltammetric cycling compared to an analogous Zn/LFP, which was tested in 4 M ZnCl_2 + 3 M LiCl [18]. We ascribe this to the specific benefits of WiSE discussed above.

3.3. LFP cathodes with different Li-ion concentrations

We investigated the dependence of the Li-ion concentration on the formal potential of LFP. Figure 3B shows the cyclic voltammograms for electrolytes containing 1.0 m and 9.5 m LiCl, respectively. (Due to solubility limitations, the ZnCl_2 concentration in the latter had to be adjusted to 9.5 m). We observe an upshift in the formal potential from 1.17 V to 1.23 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn , corresponding to a shift of 60 mV. To assess whether this shift is specific to a particular LFP material, we repeated the experiment using two additional batches of LFP with different particle size distributions. As shown in Fig. S7 (ESI), all batches exhibited similar behavior, confirming the generality of this effect. This potential shift can be explained by thermodynamic considerations. The reaction quotient corresponding to equation (3) is:

$$Q = \frac{a(\text{LiFePO}_4)}{a(\text{Li}^+)a(\text{FePO}_4)} \sim 1/a(\text{Li}^+) \quad (5)$$

where a denotes the activity of the species. From the Gibbs free energy relation and the Nernst equation:

$$\Delta G = \Delta G^\circ + RT \ln Q \equiv -F\Delta E \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta E = \Delta E^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln Q = \Delta E^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [\text{Li}^+] \quad (7)$$

where ΔE° represents the formal redox potential and $[\text{Li}^+]$ denotes the normalized Li concentration, we can determine the potential shift for different Li^+ concentrations:

$$\Delta E([\text{Li}^+] = 9.5) - \Delta E([\text{Li}^+] = 1.0) = \frac{RT}{F} (\ln 9.5 - \ln 1.0) = 57.8 \text{ mV} \quad (8)$$

These findings confirm that the formal potential of LFP shifts predictably with Li-ion concentration, in agreement with thermodynamic expectations.

3.4. Carbon-coated LMP electrode

The electrochemical performance of LiMnPO_4 in a classical Li-ion battery is known to improve significantly as a result of carbon-coating. Here we tested the carbonized material, which was developed for Li-ion batteries by HPL (Dow Chemical); it is denoted C-LMP. Figure S7 (ESI) confirms that our C-LMP exhibits the expected performance in an aprotic electrolyte solution used in Li-ion batteries, though the capacity was smaller (24 - 52 mAh/g, depending on the scan rate) than reported for the optimized C-LMP [26]. Figure 4A shows that the same C-LMP was initially quite sluggish in the Zn-dual-ion (chloride-WiSE) system, but was activated electrochemically during the subsequent 12 cycles at a medium scan rate (5 mV/s) when it reached the cathodic charge capacity of about 35 mAh/g. This performance is significantly better than that of the same material in the Li-ion system (cf. Fig. S8), but is not maintained during a subsequent slower cycling. The described electrochemical activation seems to be specific for C-LMP only; a similar material, i.e., the C-coated $\text{LiMn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{PO}_4$ does not seem to require this activation [17].

The electrochemical performance of our activated C-LMP drops if the cycling progresses at 1 mV/s (Figure 4B). The changes of charge capacities are quantified in Figures 4 C, D. Interestingly, the cathodic charges observed at 1 mV/s (between ca 40 and 25 mAh/g) are comparable or better than the capacities of the same material in aprotic Li-electrolyte (cf. Fig. S7). Also, the observed peak currents (≈ 0.2 A/g) are well comparable in both the Li-ion and Zn-dual-ion cells (cf. Fig. 4B and S8). This leads to a non-trivial finding that the rate of Li-extraction/insertion in C-LMP is virtually independent of the electrolyte type (aqueous Zn/Li-WiSE or Li-protic), i.e., the rate-controlling step is, presumably, the solid-state Li^+ -transport in C-LMP.

Yet, the aqueous (Zn-ion) system is handicapped, against the aprotic one, by anodic breakdown occurring at potentials ≥ 2.1 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . Hence, the anodic charge capacities include parasitic contributions, and cannot be used for the evaluation of C-LMP performance. The most likely cause for the anodic breakdown reactions in ZnCl_2 -WiSE is the presence of large amounts of carbon in our actual electrode materials (see Experimental Section for details) confronted with the narrow electrochemical window of GC electrode in this medium (cf. Section 3.1. and Fig. 1 above). This outlines a straightforward research challenge of finding a non-carbonaceous conductive additive which would allow extension of the electrochemical window at the anodic side. Titanium or conducting oxides (FTO, ITO, AZO) seem to be the materials of the first choice to this purpose.

3.5. Impurities in ZnCl_2

To highlight the impurity effects in ZnCl_2 , we have chosen yet another ZnCl_2 material, which was obtained from Lachner, s.r.o. Fig. 5 shows the voltammograms of LFP and pure carbon black (C65) in this medium. There is no significant difference between LFP from Roth or Südchemie, but the impurity-related features are clearly visible in the WiSE made from ZnCl_2 (Lachner). To identify the impurities, Tables S1 and S2 (ESI) present the corresponding analytical data. The main impurity in ZnCl_2 (Lachner) is Mn (0.174 wt %) and trace amounts of Mg, Al, K, Ca and Br. On the other hand, the material from Aldrich is free from impurities at the sensitivity of XRF analysis, which is in accord with the manufacturer's analytical certificate (Table S1). Figure S9 (ESI) shows that the impurities in ZnCl_2 (Lachner) can also be identified by XRD. The ZnCl_2 (Aldrich) is composed of the two known tetragonal phases of ZnCl_2 whereas the Lachner's product also contains the orthorhombic ZnCl_2 . More importantly, the diagnostic peak of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 15.5 deg (2θ) is detected solely in ZnCl_2 (Lachner) but not in ZnCl_2 (Aldrich).

Fig. 6 shows a comparison of voltammograms of blank C65 electrode in WiSE made from three different sources of ZnCl_2 , i.e. Lachner, ABCR and Aldrich. The impurity feature, assigned tentatively to MnCl_2 is apparent for ZnCl_2 (Lachner and ABCR), but not for the Aldrich product. To prove this hypothesis further, we have prepared a model WiSE from 15 m ZnCl_2 (Aldrich) to which we deliberately added MnCl_2 to a concentration of 0.17 wt% and 0.34 wt%, respectively (as referenced to the solid ZnCl_2). Fig. 6B shows the corresponding voltammograms of a blank C65 electrode in these two model media. The impurity peaks are again clearly reproduced, confirming that this effect is assignable to the presence of MnCl_2 dissolved in the electrolyte solution. Interestingly, the dissolved redox couple is electrochemically active without exhibiting the problems of sluggish electrochemistry and the need of activation, which was observed for LMP.

Conclusions

In this study, we have investigated the electrochemical performance of various electrode materials in aqueous zinc-ion batteries employing water-in-salt electrolytes. Our results highlight several critical insights into the fundamental properties of Zn-ion systems and the impact of high-concentration electrolytes on battery performance and stability.

We confirmed that electrode stability in WiSE strongly depends on the nature of the substrate material. While platinum exhibited the highest catalytic activity, it also showed the narrowest electrochemical stability window. Notably, aluminum, a popular substrate for positive electrodes of Li-ion batteries, performs worst in WiSE due to its low anodic breakdown potential. In contrast, titanium demonstrated superior anodic stability, making it a promising candidate for Zn-ion batteries. Carbonaceous materials, widely used as conductive additives, displayed electrochemical activity in ZnCl_2 -based WiSE, indicating that their role in Zn-ion batteries should be reconsidered, particularly for higher-voltage applications.

Our study demonstrated the feasibility of LiFePO_4 as a positive electrode material. The LFP electrode exhibited a reversible redox reaction at a formal potential of 1.17 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn in chloride-based WiSE, with a positive shift of 60–70 mV upon increasing Li concentration. In contrast, a shift to 1.4 V was reported in acetate-based WiSE, highlighting the significant impact of electrolyte composition on the electrochemical behavior of the positive electrode. These findings underscore the necessity of tailoring electrolyte formulations to optimize the Zn-ion battery performance.

We found that LiMnPO_4 , despite its higher theoretical voltage, exhibited inferior cycling stability compared to LFP. This discrepancy suggests that further material modifications, such as optimized Mn/Fe ratios or improved conductive coatings, may be required to fully exploit LMP's potential in Zn-ion battery.

The role of electrolyte impurities in high-concentration Zn salts has been largely overlooked in earlier literature. Our work suggests that even trace impurities can significantly affect electrochemical performance, reinforcing the need for high-purity electrolyte components in WiSE-based Zn-ion batteries.

Overall, our results contribute to the growing body of knowledge on Zn-ion systems and highlight critical factors affecting their performance. The findings emphasize the importance of material selection, electrolyte composition, and impurity control in advancing technology for practical energy storage applications. Future studies should focus on systematic screening

of electrode-electrolyte combinations, long-term cycling performance, and the development of novel materials tailored for aqueous Zn-ion batteries with improved stability and efficiency.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: MG, FTE; Data curation: TS, LK, MZ, NK, JX, WN; Formal analysis: MG, FTE, LK; Funding acquisition: MG, LK, MZ; Investigation: TS, LK, MZ, NK, JX, WN; Supervision: MG; FTE; Writing: LK

All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Data availability

Data are available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388014>

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Figure 1: Cyclic voltammograms of different blank substrates in 15 m ZnCl₂ (Aldrich) at the scan rate of 50 mV/s. Plots are offset for clarity, but the current density scale is identical for all plots except platinum, which voltammogram was zoomed out by a factor of 0.2.

Figure 2: Cyclic voltammograms in WiSE electrolyte from ZnCl₂ (ABCR) on Ti-substrates. The electrolyte composition is 15 m ZnCl₂ + 1m LiCl, unless stated otherwise. [A] LiFePO₄ (Roth)+C65, [B] LiMnPO₄ + C65, [C] blank carbon black C65, [D] blank carbon black SuperP in different electrolyte solutions. Scan rates are labelled in annotations (plots A-C) and 50 mV/s (plot D).

Figure 3: Cyclic voltammograms in WiSE electrolyte from ZnCl₂ (Aldrich) on Ti-substrates; scan rate 1 mV/s. (A) The electrolyte composition is 15 m ZnCl₂ + 1m LiCl. LiFePO₄ (Roth)+C65. Two-hundred cycles were tested, inset shows the 1st and 200th cycle for easier reading. (B) Voltammograms for different LiCl concentrations (displayed is the 20th cycle). The electrolyte composition is 15 m ZnCl₂ + 1 m LiCl (red line) and 9.5 m ZnCl₂ + 9.5 m LiCl (blue line). The LiFePO₄ used was LFP-S21 from Xiamen TOB.

Figure 4: Cyclic voltammograms of C-coated LiMnPO_4 in WiSE electrolyte from ZnCl_2 (Aldrich) on Ti-substrates. The electrolyte composition is 15 m ZnCl_2 + (Roth) + 1m LiCl. Chart [A]: initial cycling at the scan rate of 5 mV/s progressive cycling is color coded. Chart [B] subsequent cycling at the scan rate of 1 mV/s; forty cycles were tested, inset shows the 1st and 40th cycle for easier reading. Charts [C, D] show the integral charge capacity (red points anodic, blue points cathodic) during the initial and subsequent cycling (data from voltammograms shown in A, B).

Figure 5: Cyclic voltammograms of LiFePO_4 (LFP) electrodes in WiSE electrolyte. The blank electrode from pure carbon black (C65) is presented by dashed curve. [A] ZnCl_2 from (Lachner), LFP from Südchemie. [B] ZnCl_2 from (ABCR), LFP from Roth. Scan rate 20 mV/s.

Figure 6: [A] Cyclic voltammograms of blank C65 electrode in WiSE electrolyte. ZnCl_2 from Lachner, ABCR or Aldrich; rate 20 mV/s. Curves are offset for clarity, but the intensity scale is identical (see scale bar) [B] Blank C65 electrode in WiSE (Aldrich) with deliberately added MnCl_2 .